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SEGMENTATION AND CLASSIFICATION OF GEOSPATIAL OBJECTS IN REMOTE SENSING IMAGES

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Abstract:

Objective- A satellite images of the earth (or geospatial images) are critical sources of information in diverse fields such as geography, cartography, meteorology, surveillance, city planning. These images contain visual information about various natural and man-made features on or above the surface of the earth. Manual annotation of geospatial images covering even a relatively small area of the earth is a tedious task. This has necessitated research into automated annotation of geospatial images.

Design / Methodology/ Approach- An important component of this research comprises object detection methods, which are model-driven methods that seek to identify probable locations of specified features of interest or objects in geospatial images.

Findings- High Resolution remote sensing images offer a more detailed description -of the observed scene. However, most of these objects could be complex structures and surrounded by disturbing background, which make object detection and image interpretation even more difficult.

Limitations- to investigate more variations on the basic energy function to produce superpixels with other interesting properties, such as certain predetermined orientations, etc. Another direction is to change patch size as a function of local image variance. It can also use our algorithm to integrate results from different segmentation algorithms.

Practical implications- This paper inspires research scholars, industrialist and academicians who are related to geospatial objects.

Originality/Value- This paper contains different types of models used in segmentation and classification of geospatial objects as literature survey.

Keywords- geospatial images, annotation, Resolution

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

Lots of work has been done for object segmentation and detection, such as the sparse representation model, visual category filter, implicit shape model, and so on. Despite some successful applications with limited data, those methods cannot detect objects as accurately as expected due to lack of spatial and structure information. Other approaches generate multilayer structures by using textual features, wavelet transforms, or dimidiating a sequence of binary Markov random fields into a tree. However, their models suffer from errors because they concentrate on the explicit characteristics, and their criteria are not consistent across images, particularly the ones containing complicated background clutters. Moreover, those works require manual interventions more or less.

There are two domains in which visual structure in images can be analyzed, namely the spatial domain (pixel intensities), and the frequency domain (Fourier spectrum). The former has been the preferred domain for describing the structure of compound geospatial objects. Spatial analysis methods have been proposed for describing the constituents and layout of such objects. These methods usually divide an image into spatial units (closed regions, lines, etc.) through image segmentation or edge detection/linking.

Spatial relations between units are analyzed using relational models such as production systems, semantic networks, human-specified constraints or rules, and evidential reasoning. There are several obstacles to using strictly spatial analysis for the modeling and detection of compound objects. 1) Compound geospatial objects often contain a large number of parts, e.g. a harbor may contain hundreds of boats. 2) The structural relations among parts are often loose and vary from one object instance to another. In order to robustly recognize an object, this variation has to be accounted for. 3) Geospatial images are highly detailed, usually on the order of thousands of pixels in each dimension. These factors reduce the appeal of strictly spatial domain analysis methods for detecting compound objects.

1.1.1 SEGMENTATION MODELS

Segmentation is the process of partitioning an image into non-intersecting regions such that each region is homogeneous and the union of no two adjacent regions is homogeneous. For intensity images (i.e., those represented by point-wise intensity levels), four popular segmentation approaches are: threshold techniques, edge based methods, region-based techniques, and connectivity-preserving relaxation methods.

- **Threshold techniques** make decisions based on local pixel information and are effective when the intensity levels of the objects fall squarely outside the range of levels in the background. Because spatial information is ignored, however, blurred region boundaries can create havoc.
- **Edge-based methods** center around contour detection: their weakness in connecting together broken contour lines make them, too, prone to failure in the presence of blurring.
- A **region-based method** usually proceeds as follows: the image is partitioned into connected regions by grouping neighboring pixels of similar intensity levels. Adjacent regions are then merged under some criterion involving perhaps homogeneity or sharpness of region boundaries. Over stringent criteria create fragmentation, lenient ones overlook blurred boundaries and over merge.
- A **connectivity-preserving relaxation-based** segmentation method, usually referred to as the active contour model, starts with some initial boundary shape represented in the form of spline curves, and iteratively modifies it by applying various shrink/expansion operations according to some energy function. Although the energy-minimizing model is not new, coupling it with the maintenance of an “elastic” contour model gives it an interesting new twist. As usual with such methods, getting trapped into a local minimum is a risk against which one must guard; this is no easy task.

1.1.2 GRAPH CUT APPROACH

A very popular approach is based on graph cut. It minimizes an energy function consisting of a data term (computed using color likelihoods of foreground and background) and a spatial coherency term. The latter term is the length of the boundary modulated with the contrast

in the image, therefore minimizing the energy with this term has a bias towards shorter boundaries. (This behavior is sometimes referred to as the “shrinking bias”.) In particular, it is hard for the graph cut approach to segment thin elongated structures. First the user constrains some pixels to be foreground and background using brushes. The segmentation by graph cut.

II. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

2.1 NORMALIZED CUT ALGORITHM

The Existing System uses a Normalized Cut Algorithm. The normalized cut criterion measures both the total dissimilarity between the different groups as well as the total similarity within the groups. The Normalized-cut algorithm could obtain a near optimal clustering, and delineate the objects regions more accurately. Tree-cut algorithm which improves the Normalized-cut by adding a Multiscale space, to get a set of segments The segmentation begins at the first level, and then each segment is split into α sub objects in following levels iteratively by using the Normalized-cut algorithm. The features used in segmentation are intensity values. This Tree-cut cannot only strictly ensure the segments in the lower level against being beyond the bounds of segments in the upper level, but also reduce the disturbance caused by surrounding background and avoid cutting spatial coherent objects into disjoint segments. The root denotes the whole image, nodes closer to root denote larger segments, and their children nodes indicate smaller segments. Each node has to be spatial disjunctive, and the parent–child node relationships capture the recursive region embedding.

2.1.1 DRAWBACKS

It suffers from errors and not consistent.

- It has complicated background clutters.
- It requires manual interventions.

2.2 MULTISCALE SEGMENTATION ALGORITHM

The new method proposed in this being entirely unsupervised, can detect geospatial objects in remote sensing images, precisely delineate the objects boundaries, and provide an understanding of images in a meaningful way. This letter is related to recent works to a certain extent. All of the three works can simultaneously recognize and segment object classes. In

particular, our method and could represent objects in a hierarchical way, which greatly improve the interpretation efficiency. However, our method uses multiscale segmentation algorithm to build a segmentation tree for each image.

All of the nodes (segments) are taken as processing bases and represented by coherent groups of topics instead of binary classified values. This accurate description cannot only mine the latent feature information, but better reduce the effects caused by lighting changes, occlusions, and background noises in high-resolution remote sensing images. Moreover, learn the embedded relationships of object categories in images. These relationships, called taxonomic semantics in our method, are composed of common elements shared by many categories, which allow categories to be defined recursively. The advantages of these semantics are that they can express both explicit and implicit spatial configuration of categories, keep the category specific properties cross images, and do not need to classify background as a category by itself. Unlike in prior works, the training images in our case are all unlabeled and may contain multiple object categories. These fundamental differences increase the precision, robustness, and effectiveness of our method for image understanding.

2.2.1 ADVANTAGES

- Here don't need to classify the objects.
- It can reduce the effects caused by lightening changes and occlusions.
- This increase the precision, robustness and effectiveness

To be used efficiently, all computer software needs certain hardware components or other software resources to be present on a computer. These pre-requisites are known as (computer) system requirements and are often used as a guideline as opposed to an absolute rule. Most software defines two sets of system requirements: minimum and recommended. With increasing demand for higher processing power and resources in newer versions of software, system requirements tend to increase over time. Industry analysts suggest that this trend plays a bigger part in driving upgrades to existing computer systems than technological advancements.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION MODELS

It aims at discovering subcategories which are matched subtree pairs recurring in the same object category with high similarity values. As shown in Fig. 4.1, organize these subcategories to obtain the taxonomic semantics of the geospatial objects categories. After that, sort subtrees according to their edit-distance values. Then all the subcategories are simultaneously identified by matching the segmentation tree of the new image with the DAG

Fig 3.1 Overall Architecture

3.2 IMPLEMENTATION MODULES

3.2.1 SEGMENTATION TREE

A segment tree is a tree data structure for storing intervals, or segments. It allows querying which of the stored segments contain a given point. The root denotes the whole image; nodes closer to root denote sub nodes, and then their children nodes. It allows querying which of the stored segments contain a given point. It is, in principle, a static structure; that is, its content cannot be modified once the structure is built. A similar data structure is the interval tree.

A segment tree for a set I of n intervals uses $O(n \log n)$ storage and can be built in $O(n \log n)$ time. Segment trees support searching for all the intervals that contain a query point in $O(\log n + k)$, k being the number of retrieved intervals or segments.

Applications of the segment tree are in the areas of computational geometry, and geographic information systems. The segment tree can be generalized to higher dimension spaces as well. The segment tree is less efficient than the interval tree for range queries in one dimension, due to its higher storage requirement: $O(n \log n)$ against the $O(n)$ of the interval tree. The importance of the segment tree is that the segments within each node's canonical subset can be stored in any arbitrary manner.

Another advantage of the segment tree is that it can easily be adapted to counting queries; that is, to report the number of segments containing a given point, instead of reporting the segments themselves. Instead of storing the intervals in the canonical subsets, it can simply store the number of them. Such a segment tree uses linear storage, and requires an $O(\log n)$ query time, so it is optimal. A version for higher dimensions of the interval tree and the priority search tree does not exist, that is, there is no clear extension of these structures that solves the analogous problem in higher dimensions. But the structures can be used as associated structure of segment trees.

3.2.2 BUILDING SEGMENTATION TREE

The Normalized-cut algorithm could obtain a near optimal clustering, and delineate the objects regions more accurately. Here propose a Tree-cut algorithm which improves the Normalized-cut by adding a multiscale space, to get a set of segments. In the scale space, the scales S_1, \dots, S_L denoting the L image levels are decrease with scale factor α

$$S_i = \alpha^{L-i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, L.$$

As the segments generated at larger scale could indicate more overall information, then apply the Normalized-cut to obtain. Segments from the top level to the bottom level, and associated. The segment number K with scale S as follows:

$$K_i = \frac{\lceil \sqrt{W \times H} \rceil}{S_i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, L$$

Where W and H are the pixel numbers of image width and height, respectively, is the gauss ceiling function. The segmentation begins at the first level, and then each segment is split into α sub objects in following levels iteratively by using the Normalized-cut algorithm. The features used in segmentation are intensity values. This Tree-cut cannot only strictly ensure the segments in the lower level against being beyond the bounds of segments in the upper level. But also reduce the disturbance caused by surrounding background and avoid cutting spatial coherent objects into disjoint Segments.

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Fig.4.2 Segmentation Tree.

3.2.3 OBJECT CLASSIFICATION

1. Object classification is the detection and classification of any object.

2. The important difference here is twofold; first, any object, even previously unseen objects shall be classified correctly,

3. Second, the object class is an abstract class such as “car”, “fruit”, etc.

K-means Clustering:

K-Means algorithm is an unsupervised clustering algorithm that classifies the input data points into multiple classes based on their inherent distance from each other. The algorithm assumes that the data features form a vector space and tries to find natural clustering in them. Various steps in the algorithm are as follows:

1. Compute the intensity distribution (also called the histogram) of the intensities.
2. Initialize the centroids with k random intensities.
3. Repeat the following steps until the cluster labels of the image do not change anymore.
4. Cluster the points based on distance of their intensities from the centroids intensities.
5. Compute the new centroids for each of the clusters.

Graph Cut Approach:

A very popular approach is based on graph cut. It minimizes an energy function consisting of a data term (computed using color likelihoods of foreground and background) and a spatial coherency term. The latter term is the length of the boundary modulated with the contrast in the image, therefore minimizing the energy with this term has a bias towards shorter boundaries. (This behavior is sometimes referred to as the “shrinking bias”.) In particular, it is hard for the graph cut approach to segment thin elongated structures. First the user constrains some pixels to be foreground and background using brushes.

3.2.4 OBTAINING NODE PROPERTIES

When calculating the properties of all the tree nodes, treat each segment as a superposition of topics by using the latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) model. Then describe the model with the original terms “documents”, “words” and “topics.” The documents refer to the image segments. Here follow the approach of and represent images using affine covariant regions, described by scale-invariant transform descriptors, and then quantized them into approximately 2000 visual words. In addition, the quantization is performed by *k*-means clustering of regions from our data set. Then map each ellipse to a circle by appropriate scaling along its principal axes, and decide to which segments the words belong according to the coordinates of their circle centers. Define a set of *N* latent topics altogether to summarize all segments.

Fig 4.3 Lda Graphical Model

Shaded nodes are observed. *M* is the number of documents and *N_d* is the number of words in each document. What the corresponding categories of these topics are. The LDA model is learned to maximize the following likelihood:

$$p(w|\eta, \alpha, \beta) = \int p(\theta|\alpha)p(\eta|\beta) \left[\sum_z p(w|z, \eta)p(z|\theta) \right] d\theta$$

Where θ and η are multinomial parameters over the topics and words, respectively. LDA treats θ and η as random variables sampled from a Dirichlet prior. The corresponding graphical model is shown in Fig.4.2.1.3. Since the integral is intractable to solve directly, the η parameter is calculated using Gibbs sampling, and scalar hyper parameters α and β are specialized to control the mixing of the multinomial weights.

After learning the parameters of the model, define a vector γ_h to characterize the corresponding segment, denoted as node h . The vector γ_h is equal to the similarity between the visual words distribution within segment h described by multinomial parameter η_h , $p(w|\eta_h)$, and the visual words distribution within each segment to the learned multinomial weight η_c for a given topic c , $p(w|\eta_c)$. This is done by using the Kullback–Leibler (KL) divergence to compare as,

$$\gamma_h = D(p(w|\eta_h) || p(w|\eta_c)).$$

The greater the KL divergence scores are, the more probably the segment h contains the topic c , and vice versa. Thus, the property vector of each segment can be viewed as a histogram of latent topics distribution, and it provides us with two levels of semantic cues: the relationship between the topics in a node and between the nodes themselves.

IV.CONCLUSION

The advantage of this paper can achieve good performances, and even in some tough cases such as containing a large number of variations parts, object rotated in different angles, objects being partially occluded by shadows or boundary regions being blurred with background noises. The future work of this paper is to investigate more variations on the basic energy function to produce superpixels with other interesting properties, such as certain predetermined orientations, etc. Another direction is to change patch size as a function of local image variance. It can also use our algorithm to integrate results from different segmentation algorithms.

V.REFERENCES

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